

First definitions of spectral fractals and the question of RGB displays

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Abstract Fractal models enable overall control of the distribution and spatial organisation of values. Kolmogorov, then Mandelbrot, proposed the fractional Brownian motion (fBm) as a possible model linking the spatial organisation and the spatial frequencies, via the Hurst coefficient. Saupe proposed implementations in the spatial and frequency domain, and Ivanovici developed an extension to colour then multivariate images of the spatial midpoint displacement defined by Saupe. In this work we extend the fractal generation to the hyperspectral context. We also consider the rendering process for RGB displays.

Keywords Fractals, fBm, Spectral imaging

1 Introduction

Multispectral and hyperspectral imaging offer high spectral resolution measurements of the physical scene content. It also opens up various possibilities for measure extraction that goes beyond the visible domain (UV, IR, X-ray...) [3]. Spectral sensors are used in different fields, ranging from defense [9] to agricultural applications [5]. So, how can their interest be assessed as spatio-chromatic vision systems? Our hypothesis is based on the ability to assess spatial and spectral characteristics as a whole, combining spatial multi-scale and spectral multi-scale measurements. In this context, fractal models are fully adapted to serve as references. The question is: how to define them and control the metrological properties of the generated fractal image?

In this work, we recall the fractal foundations and the adapted spectral midpoint displacement for fractal generation. We then define the constraints that must be met to ensure a valid physical construction. Also, we explain how to render the generated spectral images on RGB displays. This is important for measurement systems, in which the spectral resolution overpasses the three correlated color R-G-B channels. Finally, we illustrate the multivariate image generation. A short conclusion will end this work and propose some trends.

2 Multi-spectral fractal generation using fBm

The used fractal model is based on the fractional Brownian motion (fBm) proposed by Kolmogorov [4]. The fBm (1) is linked to the fractal dimension via (3):

$$E \left((I(y) - I(x))^2 \right) = K \cdot \|y - x\|^{2H} \quad (1)$$

$$\{I(y) - I(x)\} \propto \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma) \quad (2)$$

$$D = E + n - H \quad (3)$$

where $I(x)$ is the image intensity at position x , K is a constant, $H \in [0, 1]$ is the Hurst coefficient (defines the signal or image complexity), D is the fractal dimension, E is the topological dimension of the support (1 for signal, 2 for 2D-images etc.) and n the channel count (1 for intensity images, 3 for colour images, K for multispectral or hyperspectral images). For a given scale $d = (y - x)$, the set of intensity variations is following a Gaussian or Normal distribution (2).

In this work, we chose to generate the multivariate fractal images using the midpoint displacement algorithm (MDP) described in [8]. This is an alternative to implementing the frequency generation method, which requires the use of a multivariate Fourier transform [7]. Unfortunately, no computational library of Fourier transform is over-passing three channels, meaning going beyond color images. By opposition, in the spatial domain, we are not restricted by the channel count due to the algorithm's construction. Technically, the proportionality between the recursive scaling in the MDP and the length raised to the power of H , is what gives the images their fractal properties. As for the random aspect, it is coming from the Gaussian noise.

The first extensions to color images were using a marginal approach, applying independently on each channel the uni-variate processing [2]. The multivariate extension, first used in [6] and later published in [1], is using a vectorial approach. The vectorial approach is based on a multivariate Gaussian noise inside the fractal midpoint displacement and an average location μ added after the Gaussian generation in order to control the location in a defined-positive measure space:

$$E \left((\tilde{I}(y, \lambda) - \tilde{I}(x, \lambda))^2 \right) = K \cdot \|y - x\|^{2H} \quad (4)$$

$$\left\{ \tilde{I}(y, \lambda) - \tilde{I}(x, \lambda) \right\} \propto \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma) \quad (5)$$

$$I(x, \lambda) = \mu + \tilde{I}(x, \lambda) \quad (6)$$

In a multivariate context, the Σ variance-covariance matrix expresses the correlation between the multivariate channels, allowing to explore different levels of spatio-chromatic complexity. At this step, a physical constraint must be added due to the nature of the radio-magnetic spectra or of the colour space. In the context of spectral fractal generation: $I(x, \lambda)$ is a measures, so positive defined for all the wavelengths:

$$I(x, \lambda) \geq 0 \quad \forall \lambda, \quad \text{and } \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (7)$$

In the context of colour fractal generation, the generation must be processed in CIELAB, as the color space is the only one validating an $L2$ metric between color coordinates. In this colour space, the constraint induces that the L intensity values must be positive (a et b values can be negative). These constraints impact on the selected average value μ in order to avoid cropping that would alter the nature of the Gaussian distribution.

3 Displaying multivariate images

In this section, we are considering physical spaces corresponding to real or hypothetical hyper-spectral sensors defined by their spectral sensitivity functions. By hyper-spectral sensors, we are considering a spectral sampling of the radio magnetic spectrum at each pixel location. In this initial work, we are considering perfect sensors working in the visible range ([380, 780] nm), so with a direct relationship to the CIE's standards and recommendations.

The sensors have K channels, defined by their spectral sensitivity curves $S_k(\lambda)$. As we are considering them as perfect, each channel's $S_k(\lambda)$ is sampled in the electromagnetic spectrum without inter-channel correlation. In addition, the calibration processing is applied to correct the sensitivity differences:

$$\langle S_k(\lambda), S_l(\lambda) \rangle = 0 \quad \forall k \neq l \quad (8)$$

$$\max_{\lambda} S_k(\lambda) = 1.0 \quad \forall k \quad (9)$$

These constraints allow to transpose the fractal generation in the spectral domain in addition to the spatial domain. It defines a spectral image $I(p, \lambda)$ with a given spatial resolution, and a spectral resolution associated to a spectral range (the visible range). On the other hand, the CIE recommendations state that the visible part of any spectrum can be transformed into an RGB triplet in two steps. First, the spectrum is transformed into the CIEXYZ primary space. Then, it is transposed into the RGB space accepted by the graphic system (CIERGB, Adobe RGB or in a degraded solution in sRGB).

In the first step, the CIE XYZ tristimulus values are computed by integrating the synthetic radiance image values $I(p, \lambda)$ and the CIE color matching functions (10). For convenience, we are considering that our synthetic image is constructed assuming equal-energy light as our illuminant $Ill(\lambda)$ and the k factor: $k = \frac{1}{\int_{\lambda} Ill(\lambda) \bar{y}(\lambda) d\lambda}$ is set to 1.0.

$$\begin{aligned} X(p) &= \int_{\lambda} I(p, \lambda) \bar{x}(\lambda) d\lambda \\ Y(p) &= \int_{\lambda} I(p, \lambda) \bar{y}(\lambda) d\lambda \\ Z(p) &= \int_{\lambda} I(p, \lambda) \bar{z}(\lambda) d\lambda \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Where $Ill(\lambda)$ is the illuminant spectral distribution, $I(p, \lambda)$ is the spectral image radiance and $\bar{x}(\lambda)$, $\bar{y}(\lambda)$, $\bar{z}(\lambda)$ are the CIE color matching functions.

Then, from XYZ values defined at each p location, the linear RGB values at these locations are obtained via a linear transformation matrix \mathbf{M} (11). The M matrix is relative to the selected RGB color space and the selected white reference (CIE's standard illuminants D65 or D50 ...).

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_r(p) \\ I_g(p) \\ I_b(p) \end{pmatrix} = M^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} X(p) \\ Y(p) \\ Z(p) \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Hereafter, we will name this method "spectral integration". It takes into account all the information defined in the spectral range. Another displaying approach is often

used in remote sensing and multivariate imaging, named "band-selection". In the "band-selection" approach, the color image is reduced to the selection of three colour channels in the list of K channels.

$$\begin{cases} I_r(p) = I(p, \lambda_r) & \lambda_r = \underset{\lambda}{\operatorname{argmin}}|\lambda - R_\lambda| \\ I_g(p) = I(p, \lambda_g) & \lambda_g = \underset{\lambda}{\operatorname{argmin}}|\lambda - G_\lambda| \\ I_b(p) = I(p, \lambda_b) & \lambda_b = \underset{\lambda}{\operatorname{argmin}}|\lambda - B_\lambda| \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $R_\lambda, G_\lambda, B_\lambda$ are wavelength selected to optimize the colour reproduction. Generally, they are selected according to the wavelengths related to the CIE RGB primaries, so $(R_\lambda, G_\lambda, B_\lambda) = (700, 546.1, 435.8)$ nm. To note, that Ivanovici [1] selected the wavelength of 650nm for the red channel.

4 Results and discussion

In this section, we first illustrate the generation in the colour domain to better understand the different generation parameters (μ and Σ). Then, we illustrate the generation in a seven-banded spectral domain. The two methods of colour reproduction are explored in order to assess the visual impact of each one of them. We will also show the spectra in two generation cases.

4.1 Colour fractal generation

Figure 1 shows an example of the generated color fractal images with $\mu = (60, 20, -10)^t$ and $\Sigma = \delta \cdot I$ (I : Identity matrix) in CIELAB space. As the fBm equation underlies an $L2$ metric, the generation inside an RGB color space is not exact (no valid $L2$ metric according to the physical or perceptual point of view). On the other hand, the $L2$ is valid in $CIELAB$ space. Eight complexities were considered in figure 1, from rough with $H=0.1$, to smoother with $H = 0.8$.

The fractals generated in figure 1 are based on an equi-distribution of the values on each CIELAB axis, obtained thanks to a Σ matrix proportional to the Identity matrix. Consequently, the distribution of the colour differences from the equation 4 is a sphere. When the Σ matrix is far from the Identity matrix, the colour distribution becomes an oriented ellipsoid. Figure 2, shows colour fractal images generated with the same Σ and H coefficient, but with different colour averages in CIELAB. We are observing similar complexity located around different colour averages (the same random seed was selected to improve the perception of differences). In a last illustration of colour generation in figure 3, we show several fractal images having the same H coefficient and same colour average μ , but with different Σ matrices.

4.2 Spectral fractal generation

Generating a colour fractal image is simple, we have to find a colour space where the $L2$ metric makes sense to apply the generation procedure and to transpose the result into an RGB color space. However, for spectral generation, we are working in the physical domain, reaching a theoretical fractal dimension higher than the maximal possible dimension in the colour domain. We also mention the difficulty to assess this

Figure 1: Color fractal images generated in CIELAB space and transposed in RGB color space with varying Hurst coefficient, $\mu_{CIELAB} = (60, 20, -10)^t =$ and $\Sigma_{CIELAB} = \delta_{CIELAB} \cdot I$, with $\delta_{CIELAB} = 3.0$.

physical fractal dimension: we are restricted by our displaying systems and our human visual system.

In figure 4, we are considering three spectral fractal images considering a seven-banded spectral image with $\lambda = [400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, 700]$ nm (similar to the channels captured by the SILIOS CMS-4C multispectral sensor), a covariance matrix

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 0.05 & & & & & & \\ & \ddots & & & & & \\ & & \ddots & & & & \\ & & & \ddots & & & \\ & & & & \ddots & & \\ & & & & & \ddots & \\ & & & & & & 0.05 \end{pmatrix}$$

and three Hurst coefficients: $H = [0.1, 0.5, 0.9]$. The generation is performed in the visible range. The first line in figure 4 is showing the reconstruction using a band-selection approach, while the second line is showing the reconstruction using a spectral integration, so a a more correct reconstruction aligning with the human visual system.

We are observing two main differences. First, the band selection creates false colors that are not in the initial color set (fluorescent green in this case). Second, the observed complexity is reduced using the band-selection approach facing the spectral integration approach (more uniform or quasi-uniform regions in the band-selection case). Finally, we note that we cannot observe the complexity of the generated spectral fractal image: the display can only use three primaries (channels), an industrial printer cannot reach more than 6 primaries, and our eyes use only three primaries

Figure 2: Color fractal images generated in CIELAB with the same $\Sigma = \delta_{CIELAB} \cdot I$ ($\delta_{CIE} = 3.0$), same H value (0.1) and different color average μ .

Figure 3: Color fractal images generated in CIELAB with the same color average $\mu = (60, 20, -10)^t$, $\delta_{CIELAB} = 6.0$ the same H value (0.1) but different Σ matrices.

(cones).

In figure 5, just like we did in the colour generation case in 3, we show two seven-banded fractal images having the same H coefficient and same colour average μ , but with different Σ matrices. We notice similar behavior as with colour images: Colors and observed complexities are differing as we vary the covariance matrix.

In figure 6, we visualize the influence of mean variation on the RGB rendering of four seven-banded fractal images. In figure 7, we show four pixel samples from 6. We can see the spectral signatures of the pixels and confirm that they do carry a physical meaning.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we precised how to produce multivariate fractal images. We illustrated it in the perceptual domain (colour images) and in the physical domain (hyperspectral images). We demonstrated the impact of the different parameters allowing to control the average colour or spectral location, the colour or spectral distribution thanks to the Σ variance-covariance matrix and the complexity thanks to the H Hurst coefficient. We also depicted the difficulty of obtaining a valid color reconstruction in the

Figure 4: Seven-banded fractal images with 3 different Hurst coefficients H , same spectral average $\mu = (0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$ and same Σ . On the first line, RGB colors are reconstructed by selecting 3 bands from 7, on the second line RGB colors are calculated considering the whole spectra and a spectral integration.

RGB domain. Reduced reconstruction induces errors in the colour reproduction and uncertainties in the fractal dimension assessment.

This work also illustrates the difficulty induced by the dimensional aspect: how to assess the fractal dimension of surfaces and where to apply the fractal measurement (i.e., in the physical domain (tolerance definition) and/or in the perceptual domain (sensitivity thresholds)) ? Beyond this short work, our goal is to develop calibration procedures for the measurement of non-uniform (textured) surfaces.

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Figure 5: Seven-banded fractal images with 2 different covariance matrices Σ , same spectral average $\mu = (0.8, 0.8, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.1, 0.1)$ and same $H = 0.1$. RGB colors are calculated considering the whole spectra and a spectral integration.

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Figure 6: Seven-banded multi-spectral fractal images generated with complexity $H = 0.1$, $\Sigma = (0.01, 0.01, 0.01, 0.01, 0.01, 0.01, 0.01)$ and varying means: $\mu_{red} = (0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.5, 0.8, 0.8)$, $\mu_{orange} = (0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.5, 0.5, 0.7, 0.7)$, $\mu_{green} = (0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.1)$, $\mu_{blue} = (0.8, 0.8, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.1, 0.1)$.

Figure 7: Spectral signatures of four pixels: each chosen at the same location from the four images shown in (6)